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Excellence**

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D6.2 Landscape analysis of existing training resources for the Nodes

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Definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANERIS	Operational Sensing Life Technologies for Marine Ecosystems
BINA	Biolmaging North America
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CTLS	Core Technologies for Life Sciences (Association)
EANM	European Association of Nuclear Medicine
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
EBIB	Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBO	European Molecular Biology Organization
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESMIT	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy
ESMRMB	European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology
ESOR	European School of Radiology

ESR	European Society of Radiology
EU	European Union
EUCAIM	European Federation for Cancer Images
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GBI	Global BioImaging
GerBI	German BioImaging
GloBIAS	Global BioImage Analysts' Society
ISMRM	International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
QUAREP-LiMi	Consortium for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy
RI	Research Infrastructure
RMS	Royal Microscopical Society
WMIS	World Molecular Imaging Society
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document presents a strategic analysis of training resources for Euro-BioImaging Nodes, assessing both Node-organized and global opportunities. By analyzing Node-organized and externally available training courses, alongside insights from recent surveys and training bursary applications, this report provides a foundation for strengthening the training framework of Euro-BioImaging

Delivering high-quality imaging services relies on continuous skill development, particularly as scientific advancements and technological innovations reshape the imaging landscape. While training in imaging technologies, data analysis, and facility management is available, key challenges persist:

- Limited hybrid and virtual training formats, reducing accessibility.
- Underreported training activities, impacting visibility and coordination.
- Insufficient professional development programs, especially for early-career facility staff and managers.

The EVOLVE training program has already initiated steps to address these challenges through job-shadowing, mentoring, external training support, and tailored courses. However, long-term sustainability will require strategic funding, cross-sector collaborations, and expansion of digital learning approaches. These efforts are critical to supporting the professionals who drive innovation, ensure service excellence, and uphold the highest standards in European imaging research.

1. Introduction

Although Euro-BioImaging's core mission is to provide open access to imaging technologies and expertise for scientists worldwide across all imaging scales, our ambitions extend well beyond this significant objective. We are committed to coordinating and fostering the European biological and biomedical imaging community through additional activities, including the **provision and coordination of Node staff training**. Since its establishment, our ERIC has actively promoted the training activities of our Nodes. Now, thanks to the EVOLVE project, we have the capacity to offer our own training opportunities, fulfilling a long-held aspiration.

One of the key objectives of the EVOLVE project is to provide impactful training opportunities for Node staff, focusing on topics and modalities that offer the greatest benefits for their professional development and the growth and sustainability of their facilities. The EVOLVE training program is structured around three main pillars:

1. Job Shadowing - Enabling hands-on learning through cross-Node exchanges and industry placements
2. Mentoring - Providing career guidance, professional skill-building, and leadership training
3. Euro-BioImaging-led Training Courses - Filling critical gaps in technical, data, and operational training

The Job Shadowing and Mentoring pillars are designed to complement each other, with participants in one program encouraged to engage in the other. These initiatives address specific training needs, promote the exchange of expertise and ideas, and foster community building and career development. Both programs have been launched with considerable success—the first Job Shadowing call in May 2024 and the Mentoring call in November 2024—with high participation rates and tangible impacts already being observed among participants and Nodes. These successes are being documented in our [Job Shadowing Story Series](#). Additionally, reimbursement for attending externally organized training courses in 2025 was launched in November 2024 to facilitate Node staff access to high-level training, successfully closing with 32 applicants across Euro-BioImaging Nodes. The final training activity to be introduced is Hub-organized training courses. While the first two pillars cater to the individual training needs of Node staff, this initiative aims to offer training events with broad community appeal, addressing gaps in the European training landscape for biological and biomedical imaging scientists.

The landscape analysis presented in this document is a key component of our efforts to identify which training topics and formats will have the greatest impact. However, it is equally essential that Node staff have the opportunity to articulate their training needs. To this end, we conducted the EVOLVE Survey for Nodes, which informs this Deliverable along with an analysis of a previous Node survey focussed on training needs carried out in 2022.

A comprehensive understanding of Node training priorities must be combined with a clear assessment of existing training resources to determine which topics and formats will provide the greatest impact. The European (and global) bioimaging training landscape is vast and diverse, making a structured overview crucial. This analysis serves precisely that purpose. Combined with the results of the EVOLVE survey, it provides a framework for designing Euro-BioImaging's training activities within the EVOLVE project, ensuring they are aligned with the needs of the Euro-BioImaging Node community.

2. Methodology

To conduct a landscape analysis of existing training resources for Node staff, we have compiled and analyzed relevant training courses available to the European biological and biomedical imaging community from 2019 to the present. The analysis has been categorized into three main areas:

1. Node-organized training courses
2. External training offerings
3. Surveys of training needs (2022 survey and EVOLVE survey 2024)

For this analysis, we focused on hands-on training, including practical courses, educational webinars, and workshops, while excluding scientific conferences and symposia.

2.1 Sources

The information was obtained from multiple sources, depending on the organizer and where the course was publicized. The primary source of Node training is the Nodes themselves, which offer a wide range of training opportunities. Additionally, both external and Node-organized training courses are frequently announced through the community-driven repository, [MicroscopyDB](#).

Further course information and training resources are available on several platforms that publicize training events and often host course materials. These platforms include the [Global BioImaging Training Platform](#), [MicroscopyDB](#), and [Zenodo](#). Additional sources of information include [Euro-Bioimaging Industry Training Resources](#), EU projects with a strong training component (e.g., [RItrainPlus](#), [eRImote](#), and [ANERIS](#)), and international organizations such as [EMBL](#) and [EMBO Courses and Workshops](#).

2.2 Classification of Training Courses

Special focus was given to courses and workshops in English and specifically targeted at Node staff (e.g., facility staff training, educational training), rather than solely user and introductory imaging methodology training. Additionally, distinguishing between ad-hoc and periodic courses was essential for assessing training availability for Nodes and identifying potential gaps or opportunities for future courses. Another key aspect was based on course format (e.g., in-person, virtual, or hybrid) to better define the adaptability of training materials to different training environments. Regarding training area, the offer for Node Staff was categorized as follows:

- *Technical training*: Enhances Nodes' capabilities in delivering current services and expanding into new and innovative tools and technologies. Topics include instrument training and sample or model preparation in biological and biomedical imaging technologies.
- *Core facility operations*: Improves Node management and efficiency while addressing a critical challenge within the community—staff with significant scientific expertise being required to run imaging facilities without proper training in business administration and management. Topics include quality control, outreach and communications, budgeting, accounting, and user management.
- *Professional development*: Strengthens Node staff's ability to handle challenges for which they are not traditionally trained. This includes soft skills and management skills such as leadership, negotiation, teamwork and effective communication.
- *Data management and analysis*: Equips Node staff to navigate the rapidly evolving image data landscape. Topics include image data FAIRification, image data storage, and image data analysis including AI-based tools and applications.

Courses that overlapped multiple training areas were also considered—for example, those combining technical skills with operational, data, or management aspects relevant to imaging core facilities.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Node-organized training

Information on the Node-organized training courses has been collected from 2019 to the present through direct communication with the Nodes (2019–2024). In addition, we analysed the reporting in the Euro-BioImaging Web Portal by the Nodes themselves (2019–2022) and on the embedded MicroscopyDB “[Training from our Nodes](#)” feature on the new Euro-BioImaging website launched in 2024. Due to the transition between manual collection of data from Nodes for the Euro-BioImaging website to a central collection and sharing of training course information via MicroscopyDB, the training offer in 2023 is not covered here.

3.1.1 Training areas and target audiences

The analysis of Node-organised training courses (Annex A) reveals key trends and gaps in the current training landscape. The majority of courses focus on technical topics (>60%), with data analysis (18.6%) and combined technical-data training (20.9%) making up the remainder. Training is primarily designed for users (>80%), with a significant proportion also targeting core facility staff (41.9%) and educational audiences (15.1%). Survey results from December 2022, which gathered responses from 33 participants from 15 out of 35 Nodes at the time, reinforce these findings. The data confirms that most training is directed at users (85%) and students (78%), with 41% also catering to core facility staff. However, in most of these training courses, core facility staff are a secondary audience who participate in training alongside experienced users and researchers. Very few technical trainings are solely or even primarily designed around the training needs of core facility staff. Notably, only 20% of courses extend beyond the immediate bioimaging community to include external participants from academia and industry.

In summary, both sources confirmed that training courses open for core facility staff account for 40% of the total training offering from the Nodes and that the training content primarily revolves around imaging technologies, instrument operation, and image data analysis (**Figure 1**). Given the prominence of image data analysis and management as a required skill set and demand for training in this area, the comparatively low percentage of training focussed on this topic is somewhat surprising.

These findings highlight both strengths and gaps in the current training landscape. While Nodes effectively provide technical and data analysis training for users, there is a notable lack of technical training providing for the specific training needs of core facility personnel and an even larger lack of programs addressing their broader professional development needs. Key areas such as facility management, leadership, soft skills, and operational competencies (outside instrument operation) remain underrepresented in Node training material. Given the growing need for professionalization within imaging core facilities, closing these gaps is

essential to ensuring sustainable career development and effective facility operations. External initiatives that tackle professionalisation of core facility staff will be presented in the following section of this deliverable.

Furthermore, under EVOLVE WP6, we will develop targeted training programs designed to enhance professional skills for Node facility staff. By expanding beyond technical training to include leadership, communication, and operational expertise, these initiatives aim to support the long-term growth and sustainability of the Euro-BioImaging community.

3.1.2 Training availability and distribution

To gain a deeper understanding of the training courses offered by Nodes, courses were categorized as either periodic (annual, biannual, biennial, etc.) or ad hoc. Over 58% of courses follow a periodic schedule, primarily covering core topics such as light microscopy, electron microscopy, and data analysis, with additional recurring training in super-resolution and fluorescence microscopy. Other user groups, such as those utilising MRI, PET and intravital microscopy, are also covered periodically but to a lesser extent. Conversely, 41.9% of courses are ad hoc, varying from year to year and often tailored to specific scientific communities (i.e., neuroimaging, immunology, plant imaging and metabolism). These courses also address emerging topics such as AI-driven data analysis, advanced sample preparation, and niche microscopy applications. This flexibility allows Nodes to quickly adapt to the evolving scientific and technological needs of the imaging community. However, it may also create challenges in accessibility, particularly when in-person events lack traceable materials or do not follow FAIR training practices. Establishing or linking to existing community-driven repositories of curated training resources such as the [GBI Virtual Training Platform](#) and aligning to FAIR principles, is essential to ensuring the long-term sustainability and accessibility of Euro-BioImaging's Nodes' training impact.

Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this analysis, particularly the potential for response bias, as the dataset relies on information voluntarily shared by Nodes. This may lead to the underreporting of certain training activities affecting the overall completeness and representativeness of the findings. This phenomenon particularly appears to impact upon the biomedical community, with there being a number of possible explanations. While the number of courses that address the needs of the biomedical community in this analysis is relatively low, the relative number of responding biomedical Nodes is much higher. In fact, the principal difference here is the number of courses that are organized by each individual responding Node; many more courses are organized by each individual responding biological imaging Node than by their biomedical counterparts, perhaps representing the higher number of individual applied technologies in biological imaging domains and on average a larger number of facilities comprising the biological imaging Nodes than the biomedical ones. This has a large impact in this consideration, as

training is most often organised on the institutional or facility level and only more rarely on the coordinated Node level.

Secondly, many biomedical imaging technologies, such as MRI, require accreditation on the national level before operation is possible, and, for this reason, there exists a well-established backdrop of training courses in these biomedical technologies that do not target an international audience, seeing as the accreditation would only be valid in the country providing the training. As such, these events are generally not publicised within an international community such as that fostered by Euro-BioImaging. Hands-on user training, which represents a large proportion of the training courses herein (see Figure 1), in biomedical imaging is also complicated for similar reasons, as a trainee would require accreditation in the country hosting the training to be able to work hands-on with many technologies, meaning again that such training is often conducted on local and national levels.

Regarding geographic distribution, the top six Euro-BioImaging members organizing training courses are Czechia (26.7%), the Netherlands (16.3%), EMBL (15.1%), Finland (12.8%), Denmark (10.5%), and France (7%) (**Figure 2**). While this reflects the presence of strong national infrastructures for imaging training, it also raises concerns about potential disparities in training opportunities across Euro-BioImaging Member States. In addition to the inherent issue of Node responsiveness, these imbalances highlight the need for targeted efforts to enhance accessibility, training availability, and participation from underrepresented regions, ensuring a more equitable distribution of training resources.

3.1.3 Training format and accessibility

Given the hands-on nature of most imaging techniques, more than 95% of the analysed courses here reported, are carried out in-person. It is worth noting that in the covered timeframe, the COVID-19 pandemic temporarily necessitated a shift to remote learning. However, many of these courses have since reverted to in-person delivery, reflecting the essential role of physical presence for hands-on training in imaging technologies. A second consideration may be the underreporting of virtual courses by Nodes compared to on-site courses. This discrepancy could stem from the data collection process itself and may be addressed in the future through standardized reporting via MicroscopyDB. While it is true that hybrid and virtual formats offer advantages in terms of accessibility and scalability, in-person courses remain the most effective for fostering interaction and hands-on practice. Consequently, support mechanisms — such as the support for Node staff to attend externally organized courses under EVOLVE WP6 — remain highly relevant. Ensuring access to these courses, particularly for Nodes with fewer training opportunities, is crucial for maintaining a well-trained imaging workforce across Europe.

Figure 1 | Node-organised training. Training areas (A), target audiences (B), course availability (C) and format of training (D) reported by the Nodes from 2019-2024 (excluding 2023 due to data mobilisation phase). Type of training offered showing responses from *Node Survey 2022* (E). For more detailed information on the specific courses and topics, please refer to the Euro-Biolmaging service and technology list on Node-organised training 2019-2024 (Annex A).

Figure 2 | Reported courses by Node and imaging field. Proportion of reported courses in biological and medical imaging (A), number of courses by member state since 2019 (B) and by Node (C). Note that the number of reported courses may be influenced by the date that the member state/Node joined Euro-BioImaging. For reference: CZ, NL, FI, EMBL joined in 2019; PT in 2020; DK and IL in 2021 and UK in 2022. For more detailed information on the specific courses and Nodes running them, please refer to Annex A.

3.2. Externally-organised training

Information on externally organized training courses was obtained from the websites of multiple organizing entities, including Global BioImaging and its partners, EMBO Courses and Workshops, EU projects, international societies, Euro-BioImaging partner communities, and industry. Additionally, the “[Training from our Partners](#)” feature embedded in the new Euro-BioImaging website was utilized.

3.2.1 Organizers of external imaging training

A database of external training resources, with analysis, can be found under Externally-Organized Training Courses (Annex B). It is important to mention that the dataset presented here is not absolute nor fully comprehensive of the global training landscape, as the searching tools and websites of the organizing entities were selected on preceding visibility within the European imaging community, their growing popularity in the global imaging network, and/or their relevance to training related to our partners.

Some of these organizing entities (**Figure 3**) include Global BioImaging and its partner networks, EMBL, EMBO, industry and various international associations and societies such as CTLS, RMS, ESR and WMIS. These organizations may or may not advertise their events beyond their own websites and social media channels, making it challenging to track training opportunities comprehensively. Currently, no single repository consolidates all training announcements, which can lead to difficulties in event discovery and potential redundancy. However, community-driven initiatives, such as [MicroscopyDB](#), are working to centralize information on training courses and events for the imaging community. By officially partnering with MicroscopyDB in 2024, Euro-BioImaging aims to streamline the reporting of Node training activities, improving accessibility, coordination, and the global visibility of training opportunities.

Societies and associations are another source of training courses and materials for all of our Nodes, but perhaps particularly so for the biomedical imaging community; over 50% of all courses identified as having this community as its target audience come from this source. While these data are undoubtedly impacted upon by the inherent issue of Node responsiveness, perhaps leading to an underrepresentation of Node-organized courses as mentioned above, it is nevertheless clear that they are a highly significant source of training for our biomedical Nodes. In fact, a number of these organisations have founded schools in order to satisfy the training needs of their communities; the ESR created the ESOR for radiologists and radiology technicians and the EANM founded the ESMIT for multimodality imaging and therapy. The same is true of less officially organised partner communities, such as the volumeEM, COMULISglobe and GloBIAS communities, which provide critical and highly requested trainings in topic areas such as volumeEM and related analysis, correlative and multimodal imaging, and image data analysis, respectively.

An initial source of training on the majority of technologies for Nodes will come from the instruments’ manufacturers, making industry an important source of technical training. Not only upon installation, but

also when any updates are introduced, Node staff will receive the knowledge required to run the technologies that lie at the heart of their activities from companies. It is important to note that while many companies,, run periodic courses for larger groups, the majority of this training is performed individually or with small groups of staff in a facility upon the acquisition of a technology or, thereafter, upon request, meaning that its importance in this landscape analysis is bound to be under-represented as such sessions are not announced publicly.

Figure 3 | External training courses and organisers. Number of courses by geography (A), organising entities (B) and specific institutions around the world (C). More abbreviations: Royal Microscopical Society (RMS), European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT), European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology (ESMRMB), European School of Radiology (ESOR), World Molecular Imaging Society (WMIS), International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM), Core Technologies for Life Sciences (CTLS), European Society For Molecular Imaging (ESMI), Global Biomage Analyst's Society (GloBIAS). For the used database on externally organised training see Annex B.

3.2.2 Global focus distribution and training formats

Our analysis shows that both virtual and in-person training courses are widely available across all continents, with the highest concentration in Europe and North America. While external training courses cover a broad range of topics, the majority focus primarily on technical training. Fewer courses address data analysis and operational aspects, although some do incorporate both, such as FAIR training initiatives (**Figure 4**).

As it was identified as a gap in the Euro-BioImaging Node-organised training, we focussed the global analysis particularly on available training in professional development and core facility management, with the aim to provide a more comprehensive view of available courses. Therefore, our analysis included training for research infrastructure managers, such as the RITrainPlus Continuous Professional Development courses and more specialised online courses such as the ESMIT course on building a successful theranostics team and facility. Additionally, we identified four key periodic courses designed specifically for core facility management:

- GBI Facility Management Courses (*international locations*)
- GerBI Core Facility Leadership and Management Course (*delivered by hpf-consulting in Germany*)
- CTLS Professional Development Course - Virtual (*delivered by hpf-consulting in Europe*)
- BINA Leadership and Management in Core Facilities (*Kellogg School of Management in the US*)/ (*Virtual Ed. 2022 was developed by hpf-consulting*)

These courses have gained significant popularity among core facility and RI managers due to the transferability of professional skills across scientific disciplines. In the first EVOLVE call for support for Node-staff attendance at externally organised courses (November 2024–January 2025), the GerBI Core Facility course was chosen as the preferred option for management and leadership training, with seven out of 32 applicants selecting this course. This can largely be attributed to its geographic proximity to our Nodes, as it remains the only in-person professional development course in Europe within this field. Moreover, partnering with hpf-consulting has enabled a similar training approach across GerBI, CTLS, and BINA (virtual pilot 2022). These courses, centered on communication, problem-solving, and leadership, have gained popularity due to their practical, participant-driven format, where attendees bring day-to-day challenges and core facility staff serve as trainers. Nonetheless, relying on a single consulting group for professional development across diverse regions presents risks. A uniform approach may fail to address regional challenges, limiting its effectiveness. It also reduces exposure to alternative management strategies and risks bias in taught methodologies. Over-dependence on one provider can lead to redundancy, monopoly formation, and create vulnerability if services are discontinued. To enhance impact, diversifying training providers, tailoring content to regional needs, and integrating peer-led learning are essential. On the other

hand, this aligns with GBI's goal of organizing international training courses with both local and global providers to ensure relevance, engagement, and sustainability.

In considering this landscape it is important to bear in mind a further training resource for Node staff that is not represented within the data here; on-demand, self-paced online training materials. Although they have not been counted as courses in this analysis, as the format and type of interaction with the trainer is very different, this type of material is worthy of mention and has a role to play in the training of Node staff. On-demand training materials are hosted on an online platform, such as the [GBI Virtual Training Platform](#), [Microtutor](#) and the website of the [ESOR](#), and are either the result of the material from a specific workshop/event being shared for further participants to benefit from, or are specifically created to be accessed in this manner. Some technical training on specific technologies and instruments can also be accessed in this manner with many companies, providing online and on-demand training materials, in most cases exclusively to their customers.

3.2.3 Training availability of external courses

While our dataset includes both periodic and ad-hoc training, periodic courses provide a more consistent representation of available training opportunities for Node staff. However, ad-hoc courses offer valuable insights into emerging trends and specialized training needs, these are commonly organised by international societies and consortia and/or in the frame of EU-funded projects (e.g. AI4Life, EUCAIM, eRImote, ANERIS, etc..). In technical training, ad-hoc events often mirror Node-organized courses, catering to specific scientific communities (e.g., LINdoscope: Neuroimaging and Data Analysis, Imaging Marine Organisms Across Scales, Imaging of Infection, Immune Cell Imaging Webinar Series). In the biomedical imaging field, the Early Professionals Forum Webinar Series, organized by the World Molecular Imaging Society (WMIS), serves as a professional development initiative.

Industry-led training also plays a role in external training opportunities, though many offerings are restricted to customers. In our analysis, we highlighted only open-access industry-led training, particularly virtual webinars focused on technical training or data analysis. Additionally, through the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board, Euro-BioImaging regularly features [Industry resources for Nodes](#) on its website, with most sessions conducted virtually and on an ad-hoc basis.

Figure 4 | Externally organised training based on imaging area and core topics. Proportion of topics of the external training portfolio following classification described in methodology (A): Professional development, Operations, Data Management and Technical, also the dual technical and data is considered. Training resources according to areas of imaging (B) and training format (C). Data from Externally Organised Training Courses (Annex B).

3.3. Node Training needs

To address the training requirements of Node staff, we analysed the responses from two separate surveys: the *EVOLVE Survey 2024* and the *Node Training Survey 2022*. In the following section we review the insights from our Nodes regarding priority areas on training courses, as well as materials and resources for training.

The EVOLVE Survey (training-course-related responses available in Annex C) was conducted between June and September 2024, gathering 52 responses from representatives across 24 Nodes (out of 41 Euro-BioImaging Nodes). The survey covered a wide range of topics, providing insights into training needs, including job shadowing, mentoring, training courses, core facility services and management, and green and sustainable research infrastructures (RIs).

To gain a better understanding of the diverse needs of Node staff, training areas were categorized according to the methodology outlined in this document. The survey assessed priorities in technical training, data management, core facility operations, and professional development, while also allowing respondents to indicate additional areas of interest not explicitly listed. The results offer a clearer picture of Node training priorities (**Figure 4**).

It is important to note that the answers to the survey were not limited to one, and the Nodes had the freedom to vote for more than one topic area they considered as priority, which is reflected on the mentioned percentages. In the area of technical training, the top three topics of interest were advanced light microscopy (56%), animal imaging (48%), and ex vivo, material, and plant imaging (36%). Comparing these results to the 2019–2024 Node-organised training landscape, we confirm a strong and well-supported interest in advanced light microscopy, for which Nodes already provide a substantial number of courses. In contrast, animal imaging and plant imaging courses are less frequently available but are periodically offered at the Nodes in Czechia, EMBL, the Netherlands, and Finland.

Other key technical training priorities included data analysis and processing (64.6%), protocol development (56.3%), and sample preparation (54.2%). Both Node-organised and externally organised training courses already cover these topics through workshops and practical sessions, although there does appear to be a particular gap between the demand for and availability of data analysis and management training.

In line with the *EVOLVE survey*, an earlier survey on Training for Nodes was performed in December 2022 with 15 out of 35 Nodes responding, providing a total of 33 individual responses. In the *Node Training Survey 2022*, more than 60% of surveyed facilities expressed interest in advanced training for imaging technologies, with Image Data Management and Image Analysis being particularly in demand. Furthermore, 48% of respondents indicated an interest in Core Facility Management training, while 39% expressed a need for Job Shadowing opportunities (**Figure 4**, Facility training needs). These findings reiterate the importance of the training initiatives supported by EVOLVE.

In terms of core facility operations, the most relevant topics identified were quality control of imaging core facilities (67.3%) and data management (63.3%). While QUAREP-LiMi provides guidelines for implementing quality control protocols for specific aspects of light microscopy systems and protocols for medical imaging are well-established and integrated into facility operations, a universal quality control training program tailored to imaging facilities remains unavailable. Such a program could address quality management not just at the instrument level but across entire facilities' operations. This gap presents an opportunity to develop a training program, potentially leveraging ISO 9000 standards adapted to the operational framework of imaging core facilities. On the subject of data management training, Euro-BioImaging Hub staff regularly organize [FAIR Data training workshops](#), and the global imaging data community continues to introduce new resources, such as initiatives from GloBIAS and GBI training courses on data management.

Consistent with our analysis of Node-organised training, there is a notable lack of professional development courses for Node staff. The most requested topic in this category was "Train-the-Trainer: The Toolkit to Develop Your Own Courses and Workshops" (58.1%), followed by "How to Talk to Your Funders" (55.8%) and "Time Management and Proactive Communication for Early Imaging Core Facility Staff" (53.3%). These topics have now been incorporated into the Euro-BioImaging Training Plan for Professional Development (EVOLVE Milestone 6.1), ensuring that future training initiatives better address the evolving needs of our Nodes. In terms of improving communication and outreach with users, an expert group on the subject is coordinated by the Euro-BioImaging External Communications's Officer, to which Node staff are regularly invited to participate and receive training on a range of communications tools and can share best practices amongst each other.

The *Node Training Survey 2022* revealed a preference for in-person, hands-on training conducted at Node facilities. However, 50% of respondents also expressed a willingness to use pre-existing training materials for self-directed learning or to integrate them into their own courses. This indicates a growing need for a flexible, diverse training approach that combines practical, on-site experiences with accessible learning resources that can be adapted to various training settings. For instance, making use of self-paced training on existing virtual platforms like [Microtutor](#), dedicated to interactive virtual light microscopy education. It is worth noting, however, that this survey was held within the first few years of our ERIC's lifetime and against the backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic, potentially influencing results.

In addition to the surveys, the actual applications submitted through the EVOLVE call for *Bursary Support for External Training Courses* (running from November 2024 to January 2025) provide valuable insight into the training needs and interests of our Nodes.

Of the 32 total applicants, 25% applied for professional development courses. Notably, all but one of these applications were for the *GerBI Core Facility Leadership and Management Course*, delivered by hpf-consulting in Germany. The remaining application was for either the *GloBIAS Training School* or the *GBI Train-the-Trainer 2025*. The majority of applications fell into two other categories: data analysis (20%) and technical training (55%). Among technical training requests, the most in-demand technologies, ranked by application volume, were fluorescence microscopy, electron microscopy, confocal microscopy, and cryo-electron tomography.

These results highlight a strong demand for leadership training alongside specialized technical skills, particularly in advanced microscopy techniques. The significant interest in professional development courses suggests that many Node members are looking to enhance their managerial and leadership competencies, which are crucial for running core facilities effectively. Meanwhile, the high number of technical training requests underscores the continuous need for expertise in cutting-edge imaging technologies. This data will be instrumental in shaping future training initiatives, ensuring they align with the evolving needs of our community.

Node Imaging Technical Training

Other Technical Training

Core-Facility Operation Training

Soft Skills and Professional Development Training

Nodes overall training interests (Node Training Survey 2022)

Figure 5 | Node training priorities. Node responses submitted to the *EVOLVE Survey 2024* and *Node Training Survey 2022*.

3.4 Job shadowing and Mentoring

As part of the training initiatives ongoing within EVOLVE and complementary to the training courses for Nodes, the launching of the first job shadowing and mentoring programs aims to enhance expertise, provide on-the-job learning opportunities, and increase collaboration within our research infrastructure and across other imaging networks.

3.4.1 Job Shadowing

The Cross-Node Job Shadowing enables staff exchanges between Nodes, allowing participants to gain valuable insights, expertise, and best practices from their counterparts. Through this initiative, Node staff members have the opportunity to visit other Nodes, collaborate with their teams, and enhance their knowledge in scientific, technical, operational, and management fields, including data management.

The topics that were selected by our fellows were facility management, user support, image data analysis and management, electron microscopy, correlative imaging and EU project management. Some [successful stories of our job shadowing fellows](#) are now available through our website.

The program offers significant benefits at both the individual and organizational levels. For individual staff members, it provides a chance to develop new technical and operational skills, particularly in very specialised and hands-on areas such as protocol development and sample preparation, experience different work environments, and expand professional networks. At the Node level, the program promotes technical and operational development, stimulates participation in collaborative projects, and helps standardize and improve administrative procedures. By fostering knowledge exchange and strengthening connections among Node staff across Europe, the Cross-Node Job Shadowing program plays a crucial role in reinforcing Euro-BioImaging's mission.

3.4.2 Mentoring

Euro-BioImaging's Mentoring Program aims to strengthen the imaging community by fostering connections among staff from different Nodes and the Global BioImaging network. This initiative supports both mentors and mentees by enhancing soft skills and providing career guidance.

Launched in November 2024, the program brought together 15 mentor-mentee pairs representing 15 nationalities across all continents. It officially kicked off in January 2025 and will run for six months, featuring virtual mentoring sessions and specialized masterclasses. These sessions will cover topics such as negotiation, business strategy and entrepreneurship in imaging core facilities, management and soft skills for imaging scientists, leadership and negotiation in medical imaging, and women in science.

Among the 29 applicants, key mentoring priorities included career development, professional counseling, data management strategies, and leadership skills. On the technical side, the most requested topics by mentees were advanced light microscopy, electron microscopy, and fluorescence microscopy, along with specific interest in spatial transcriptomics and X-ray phase contrast imaging.

By bringing together a diverse group of professionals and providing tailored mentorship, the program is not only strengthening individual career paths but also fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange across the imaging community. The strong demand for both professional development and advanced technical expertise reflects the shifting landscape of imaging science, where continuous learning and interdisciplinary skills are becoming increasingly essential. As the program progresses, it is expected to create lasting connections, inspire future mentoring initiatives, and contribute to the continued growth of imaging science worldwide.

Figure 6 | Building a network of expertise and collaboration through training. First call of Euro-BioImaging Cross-Node Job Shadowing displaying a total of 24 applications within 21 Nodes across 11 member states and EMBL (A). Euro-BioImaging fosters relationships with the global imaging network via its Mentoring Program with 15 pairs of mentors and mentees actively participating in virtual mentoring sessions and masterclasses (B). Candidates profile for Job Shadowing program call 2024 (C).

Conclusions and future recommendations

Training for Node staff is essential to delivering high-quality services and ensuring that facilities operate at the highest standards. This benefits not only Euro-BioImaging users but also the large number of local users from hosting institutions who access these facilities and receive training from facility staff. Consequently, enhanced training for Euro-BioImaging Node staff provides added value to hosting institutions through their affiliation with Euro-BioImaging.

Importantly, training and continuous professional development play a critical role in job satisfaction and retention of staff in facilities. This impacts their local ecosystems by ensuring that investments in staff recruitment and training are not wasted and prevents brain-drain. With facilities increasingly recognized as key drivers of efficient, high-quality research in large institutions, and with continuous technical advancements, qualified core facility staff are more valuable than ever.

New facility staff, often coming from research backgrounds, typically lack formal training in service provision and core facility operations. Ensuring they receive the necessary training is a major focus for facilities and can be a time-intensive process. Therefore, making a wide range of training resources accessible to core facility staff is crucial to maintaining the overall health of the infrastructure and its components.

The analysis of Node-organized and external training resources presented in this deliverable reveals key areas in the current imaging training landscape, notably the strong emphasis on hands-on technical training and its capacity to address emerging scientific needs. Existing offerings provide coverage of core imaging technologies and data analysis, ensuring that both users and core facility staff have access to a wide range of learning opportunities.

However, several aspects must be addressed to enhance the overall training impact for our Nodes and their users. For example, the limited adoption of hybrid and virtual learning formats by the reporting Nodes restricts training accessibility, particularly for those unable to attend in-person sessions. Also a connecting issue is the underreporting of training activities by the Nodes, and a lack of responsiveness when surveying training needs.

Most notably, the absence of professional development courses for early-career core facility staff represents a significant gap. While core facility management courses are periodically offered by external providers (although with limited accessibility due to costs and restricted participation), the specific needs of early-career staff require more targeted formats, such as train-the-trainer programs and virtual/hybrid training options. Furthermore, diversifying training providers, tailoring content to regional needs, and incorporating peer-led learning could enhance the relevance, engagement, and long-term impact of these programs. Addressing these gaps is critical for fostering a more robust, future-proof training ecosystem that meets the evolving demands of the imaging community.

Euro-BioImaging aims to continue its training mission beyond the conclusion of EVOLVE, focusing on an integrated professional development program for Nodes. This effort will involve launching and coordinating comprehensive training on advanced technologies and trends, image data, user access, quality management, software tools, facility organization, instrument procurement, budgeting and administration, and staff hiring and management. Additionally, a dedicated training school for early-career core facility staff will be established, emphasizing core facility management and essential soft skills. However, given the diversity of training needs and the imaging landscape, external training courses play an important role in addressing the Nodes training needs and will continue to do so. To ensure that excellent external training is accessible to all Euro-BioImaging Nodes, provision of support for Node staff to attend such courses is critical. This plays an important role in levelling the playing field and ensuring that Node staff, independent of their facilities' training budget, can receive the technical training they need to provide excellent user services.

To further advance career growth and collaboration, Euro-BioImaging will continue its job-shadowing and mentoring programs under EVOLVE, enabling Node staff across Europe to collaborate on technological advancements, joint projects, and the development of new core facility services, including international and cross-Node initiatives. Moreover, through the Mentoring Program and GBI Working Groups, Euro-BioImaging will collaborate with global partners and national imaging communities to advocate for the recognition and advancement of core facility staff roles and career pathways. Job shadowing and mentoring were consistently one of the most listed needs from Nodes, and the strong participation in the first round of both programs underscores their demand and value. The already visible impact, on the individual participants, but critically also on the overall sense of community and collaborative networking across the European Research Area, highlights the importance of these programs. Their continuation beyond the EVOLVE framework will therefore be critical.

However, sustained investment is crucial to ensure the long-term impact and scalability of these initiatives currently enabled by EU funding through EVOLVE until mid of 2027. Continued funding will enable greater accessibility to training, the development of structured career pathways for core facility staff, and the adaptation of course content to emerging imaging technologies and evolving scientific needs. Without dedicated resources, training opportunities will become limited and their accessibility will be reduced, reducing in turn their impact and hindering the development of the next generation of imaging professionals. Investing in training not only strengthens Euro-BioImaging's mission but also cultivates high-quality imaging expertise across Europe, driving long-term innovation and scientific excellence.

To further enhance the accessibility and impact of Euro-BioImaging's training programs, several key initiatives are already being prioritized by Euro-BioImaging ERIC. These include mobilizing Node-organized training materials to the Global BioImaging Virtual Training Platform and creating a dedicated entry point on the Euro-BioImaging website. This ensures that training courses organised by the Node experts with local resources gain improved visibility and their impact is increased. This portal will link the Node-developed

training material with training materials from Hub-organized courses (e.g., FAIR training), EU projects in which our RI organises trainings (e.g., AI4Life, eRImote, ANERIS), and materials developed by Node Experts in the framework of Euro-BioImaging's Expert Groups (e.g., the SMART Microscopy and Human Imaging groups). These activities will be aligned with FAIR principles to ensure the long-term sustainability and accessibility of Euro-BioImaging's training efforts.

In summary, securing targeted funding and support is essential for sustaining the ongoing critical work in EVOLVE for providing training for Node staff, and making Node-organised training visible, as well as for expanding training opportunities and increasing access in underrepresented regions. Investing in digital training formats, including hybrid and virtual options, will significantly extend reach and flexibility, making high-quality training accessible to a broader audience. Additionally, strengthening engagement with underrepresented Nodes will help ensure that all parts of the Euro-BioImaging community benefit from diverse and high-impact training programs. Collectively, these efforts will be crucial in enhancing the sustainability, inclusivity, and long-term growth of Euro-BioImaging's training initiatives and underpin Member States' existing investments in their national imaging infrastructures.

Annexes

Annex A - Node Organised Training Courses																	
Bio/Med	Member	Node	Name of the course	Area	Target audience	Weblink	Location	Format	Course schedule (usually)	More specific dates	Teaching approach	Euro-Biomed technology / service	Training availability	Technologies/services (corresponding to ratified list)	Keywords	Keywords (more concise)	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Microscopy Methods in Biomedicine	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Educational training	http://www.microscopytraining.eu/courseimaging/	Institute of Molecular Genetics, Prague	In-person	Autumn	12-16 Oct 2020	theoretical and hands-on	SDCM; TIRF; STED; PALM; STORM; FRET; EM; Data processing and analysis	Ad hoc	SDCM, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FRET, EM, Image processing and data analysis	light microscopy, electron microscopy	light microscopy, electron microscopy, image analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Single Molecule - Microscopy and Manipulation	Technical	User training, Educational training	http://imcf.natur.cuni.cz/SM/MM/	BIOCEV, Prague	In-person	Autumn	January 18-22, 2021	theoretical and hands-on	FCS, TIRF, optical tweezers, STED	Ad hoc	FCS, TIRF, STED	fluorescence microscopy, single molecule	fluorescence microscopy, single molecule	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Measurement of biological structures for engineers	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Educational training	https://www.czech-bioimaging.cz/files/PDF/courses-measurement-of-biological-structures-for-engineers-24-25-10-2017-web.pdf	Institute of Physiology CAS, Prague	In-person	Autumn	24-25 Oct 2020	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM, DWM, MMS, SDCM, FLIM, OPT,	Ad hoc	LSCM, DWM, MMS, SDCM, FLIM, OPT,	Light microscopy, Fluorescence microscopy, Functional Imaging, Image analysis	Light microscopy, Fluorescence microscopy, Functional Imaging, Image analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Transmission Electron Microscopy in Life Sciences	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	http://www.microscopytraining.eu/coursetem/	Institute of Molecular Genetics, Prague	In-person	Winter	25-29 Nov 2020	theoretical and hands-on	EM	Periodic	EM	electron microscopy; transmission electron microscopy; TEM	electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Processing and analysis of microscopic images in biomedicine	Data Analysis	User training, Educational training	http://www.microscopytraining.eu/imageprocess/	Institute of Molecular Genetics, Prague	In-person	Spring	23-27 Nov 2020	theoretical and hands-on	Data processing, data analysis	Ad hoc	Image processing and data analysis	image data; data processing; data analysis	image data, data processing, data analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	FLIM not only for biologists	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	http://imcf.natur.cuni.cz/FNOB/	BIOCEV, Prague	In-person	Winter	10-12 February 2021	theoretical and hands-on	FLIM	Periodic	FLIM	Functional Imaging, Fluorescence microscopy, data analysis	Functional Imaging, Fluorescence microscopy, data analysis	
Medical Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	In vivo imaging in animal models	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training		Institute of Physiology, CAS, Prague	In-person		TBD (Q2-Q3)			Ad hoc		Live animal imaging/2P	animal imaging, large samples, multiphoton	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Technical aspects of experiments using advanced light microscopy	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training		Prague	In-person		3-4 November 2021			Ad hoc		2P/OPT/design of experiment	design of experiment, methods comparison, image processing and analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Virtual Reality tools in biology data analysis	Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training		Prague	In-person		TBD (Q4)			Ad hoc		Virtual Reality	microscopy images, virtual reality, image processing and analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	3D-CLEM Imaging function and ultrastructure	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training		BIOCEV, Vestec	In-person		22-25 November 2021			Ad hoc		CLEM, EM, CLSM, MMS, QPI, SDCM	FIB-SEM, sample preparation, 3D data visualization, correlative imaging, multi-modal imaging, confocal microscopy practical course, specimen preparation, high pressure freezing, plunge freezing, freeze substitution, immunogold labeling, sectioning, negative staining	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Biology Specimens in Electron Microscopes	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training		Institute of Parasitology, BC CAS, Ceske Budejovice	In-person		TBD (4-8 October 2021)			Ad hoc		TEM, electron tomography, SEM, cryo-SEM, SBF-SEM, array tomography		
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	EMBO Practical course: Super-resolution in light microscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://meetings.embo.org/event/20-superresolution-microscopy	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR - Prague	In-person	yearly	May 31 - Jun 6, 2020	theoretical and hands-on	Stimulated emission depletion microscopy (STED), Photo activated localization microscopy (PALM), Stochastic optical reconstruction microscopy (STORM), Reversible saturable optical fluorescence transitions (RESOLFT)	Periodic		STED; SIM; SMLM - Palm and STORM; Optical reassignment		
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Superresolution in Light Microscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://course.img.cas.cz/sim/	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR	In-person	Autumn	25-27 November 2019	theoretical and hands-on	STED; SIM	Periodic	STED	SIM; STED; superresolution techniques; light microscopy; course; practical; Prague	super-resolution techniques, light microscopy, SIM	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Microscopy Methods in Biomedicine	Technical	User training, Educational training	http://www.microscopytraining.eu/courseimaging/	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR	In-person	Autumn	14-18 Oct 2019	theoretical and hands-on	SDCM; TIRF; STED; PALM; STORM; FRET; EM; Data processing and analysis	Ad hoc	SDCM, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FRET, EM, Image processing and data analysis	light microscopy, electron microscopy	light microscopy, electron microscopy	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Mechanical characterization of biological samples using correlative methods	Technical	User training, Educational training	https://biomaging.fu.cas.cz/event/mechanical-characterization-of-biological-samples-using-correlative-methods/	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR	In-person	Autumn	14-18 Oct 2019	theoretical and hands-on	SDCM; TIRF; STED; PALM; STORM; FRET; EM; Data processing and analysis	Ad hoc	SDCM, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FRET, EM, Image processing and data analysis	light microscopy, electron microscopy	light microscopy, electron microscopy	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Live Cell Imaging	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://course.img.cas.cz/lci/	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR	In-person		2024	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM, DWM, MMS, SDCM, FLIM, OPT,	Ad hoc	LSCM, DWM, MMS, SDCM, FLIM, OPT,	Light microscopy, Fluorescence microscopy, Functional Imaging, Image analysis	Light microscopy, Fluorescence microscopy, Functional Imaging, Image analysis	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague	Image Data Presentation	Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://course.img.cas.cz/idx/	Institute of Molecular Genetics ASCR	In-person		2024	theoretical and hands-on	Data processing, data analysis	Ad hoc	Image processing and data analysis	image data; data processing; data analysis	image data, data processing, data analysis	

Annex A - Node-Organised Training Courses

Medical Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	NeuroImaging: Mapping the function and structure of brain	Technical	Educational training	https://www.celetec.eu/educational-courses/neuroimaging-mapping-the-function-and-structure-of-brain-2020/a3971	Multimodal and Functional Imaging laboratory (MAFIL), CEITEC MU	In-person	Autumn (once a year)	24-26/11/2020	theoretical and hands-on	(Micro)-MRI, High-field MRI	Periodic	High-field MRI, Micro-MRI	fMRI, VBM, DTI, neuroimaging, MRI, SPM, data processing, electrophysiology, EEG, simultaneous EEG-fMRI, NIBS, preclinical	neuroimaging, MRI, electrophysiology, simultaneous EEG-fMRI, preclinical
Biological Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	Introduction to fluorescence microscopy: from sample preparation to image acquisition	Technical, Data Analysis	User training	https://www.celetec.eu/introduction-to-fluorescence-microscopy-from-sample-preparation-to-image-acquisition/a3791	CEITEC MU	In-person	twice a year, next on Autumn	19-20 November 2019	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM/CLSM; Deconvolution widefield microscopy	Periodic	LSCM, DWM	optics; fluorescence microscopy; sample preparation; image acquisition; widefield microscopy; confocal microscopy; deconvolution; 3D reconstruction	optics, fluorescence microscopy, sample preparation, image acquisition, 3D reconstruction
Biological Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	Advanced live cell imaging and cell tracking	Technical, Data Analysis	User training	not available yet	CEITEC MU	In-person	Spring		theoretical and hands-on	LSCM/CLSM; FRAP; Phase contrast imaging	Ad hoc	LSCM, FRAP, Image processing and data analysis	live cell imaging; organelles; fluorescent proteins; cell culture; cell tracking; IMARIS; Fiji-Imagej; TrackMate	live cell imaging, organelles, cell tracking, IMARIS, ImageJ, TrackMate
Biological Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	Super-resolution spinning disc microscopy	Technical	User training	https://www.celetec.eu/super-resolution-spinning-disc-microscopy-principles-advantages-and-limits/a3863	CEITEC MU, Brno	In-person	single time	March 10-11, 2020	theoretical and hands-on	SDCM	Ad hoc		spinning disc, superresolution	
Biological Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	Fundamentals of Light Microscopy	Technical, Data Analysis	User training	https://www.celetec.eu/fundamentals-of-light-microscopy/a4106	CZ - Masaryk University - CEITEC	In-person	twice a year	November 8-11, 2021	theoretical and hands-on	Laser scanning confocal microscope (LSCM / CLSM), Deconvolution widefield microscopy	Periodic			widefield microscopy, confocal microscopy, image analysis, light microscopy
Biological Imaging	CZ	Multimodal Imaging Node Brno	Processing and Analysis of Biological Images: Focus on Cell Tracking	Data Analysis	Educational training	https://www.celetec.eu/processing-and-analysis-of-biological-images-focus-on-cell-tracking/a3961	Virtual (organised by Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Node Brno CZ)	Virtual	Winter	11.-13. Nov 2020	theoretical	LSCM/CLSM, SDCM, DWM, FRET, FRAP, Image analysis	Ad hoc	LSCM/CLSM, SDCM, DWM, FRET, FRAP, Image analysis	Image analysis, 3D reconstruction, Cell Tracking	Image analysis, 3D reconstruction, Cell Tracking
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Advanced Live Cell Imaging	Technical	Educational training	https://cab.ku.dk	University of Copenhagen	In-person	every 2 years	June 27 - July 1, 2022	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, FRAP, Raman spectroscopy, High-throughput microscopy	Periodic		Mammalian cells; plants; microorganisms	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Cross Institutional Bioluminescence Ph.D Course	Technical	Educational training	https://dambic.dk/index.php?page=Cross-institutional-Bioluminescence	University of Southern Denmark	In-person	yearly	TBD	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FCS, FCCS, FLIM, FRET, FRAP, Raman spectroscopy, High-throughput microscopy, (Micro)-PET, (Micro)-SPECT, (Micro)-PET/CT, (Micro)-SPECT/CT, CARS, SIM, XRF	Periodic		interdisciplinary; live cell imaging; spinning disc microscopy; electron microscopy; photoactivated localization microscopy; single particle techniques; structured illumination; stimulated emission depletion microscopy; Image analysis	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Biophotonics	Technical	Educational training	https://dambic.dk/index.php?page=BMB207	University of Southern Denmark	In-person	yearly	January 17-21 2022	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Multiphoton microscopy systems, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, FRAP, High-throughput microscopy, CARS, SIM	Periodic		bioimaging; hands on; fluorescence; image analysis; super resolution; multiphoton; CARS; STORM	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Principles in Light and Confocal Microscopy - PhD course	Technical	Educational training	https://cfim.ku.dk/events/principles-in-light-and-confocal-microscopy---phd-course---august-2021/	The Core Facility for Integrated Microscopy, Univ. of Copenhagen	In-person	twice a year	January 10-28 2022	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FCS, FRET, FRAP, SPIM, SIM	Periodic		Light Microscopy; Köhler illumination; conjugated planes; diffraction and resolution; interference colours; advanced fluorescence microscopy; super resolution; SPIM; F-words; live imaging; laser scanning microscopy	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Image Processing PhD course	Data Analysis	Educational training	https://cfim.ku.dk/events/image-processing-phd-course-2021/	The Core Facility for Integrated Microscopy, Univ. of Copenhagen	In-person	yearly	June 20-24 2022	theoretical and hands-on	Image analysis	Periodic		Image processing; Fiji; cell Profiler; Ilastik; machine/deep learning pixel and object classification	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Electron Microscopy - PhD course	Technical	Educational training	https://cfim.ku.dk/events/electron-microscopy---phd-course/	The Core Facility for Integrated Microscopy, Univ. of Copenhagen	In-person	yearly	October 10-21 2022	theoretical and hands-on	EM	Periodic		TEM; SEM; Cryo-TEM; serial block face; negative stain; sample preparation; Tomography	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Crash course in Light Microscopy	Technical	User training	https://cfim.ku.dk/events/light-microscopy-two-day-crash-course-january-2022/	The Core Facility for Integrated Microscopy, Univ. of Copenhagen	In-person	twice a year	25.04.2022, -26.04.2022	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM	Periodic		Light Microscopy; conjugated planes; diffraction; Köhler illumination; confocal microscopy; fluorescence	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Biological imaging	Technical	User training	https://phdcourses.ku.dk/DetailKursus.aspx?id=10868&sitepath=NAT	University of Copenhagen	In-person	yearly	25.04-22.06.2022	theoretical and hands-on	FLIM, STORM, STED, PALM, EM, X-ray imaging, image analysis	Periodic		fluorescence microscopy, fluorescence life time imaging, super resolution microscopy, electron and cryo electron microscopy, X-ray imaging	
Biological Imaging	DK	Danish Bioluminescence Node	Advanced Live Cell Imaging	Technical	User training	https://www.danishbioluminescence.dk	University of Copenhagen	In-person	every 2 years	June 27 - July 1, 2022	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, FRAP, Raman spectroscopy, High-throughput microscopy	Periodic		Mammalian cells; plants; microorganisms	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Bioluminescence EMBL-Node	Fundamentals of Widefield and Confocal Microscopy and Imaging	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.de/training/events/2021/MIC21-01/index.html	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Spring/Summer	31 May - 04 June 2021	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM/CLSM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, FRAP	Periodic	LSCM, DWM, FRAP	fundamentals of light microscopy; transmission contrast methods; fluorescence microscopy; laser scanning confocal microscopy; FRAP	fundamentals of light microscopy, widefield microscopy, transmission contrast methods, fluorescence microscopy

Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Advanced Fluorescence Imaging Techniques	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.de/training/events/2021/MJC21-02/index.html	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Spring/Summer	6 - 11 June 2021	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM/CLSM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, TIRF, STORM, FRET, FRAP	Periodic	LSCM, DWM, TIRF, STORM, FRET, FRAP. Image processing and data analysis	TIRF; widefield deconvolution microscopy; laser-scanning confocal microscopy; Super-Resolution Microscopy; image analysis; FRAP; FRET;	super-resolution microscopy, image analysis
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Super-Resolution Microscopy: Time-Resolved STED Nanoscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/mic21-03	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Summer	12 - 16 July 2021	theoretical and hands-on	STED	Periodic	STED	super-resolution microscopy	super-resolution microscopy
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Advanced Electron Microscopy for Cell Biology	Technical	User training	https://www.embl.de/training/events/2020/EMM20-01/index.html	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Spring/Summer	16-26 June 2020	theoretical and hands-on	EM	Ad hoc	EM	EM, sample preparation, Tokuyasu, TEM, ultramicrotomy	sample preparation, Tokuyasu, TEM, ultramicrotomy
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Volume Electron Microscopy by Automated Serial EM	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.de/training/events/2019/EMT19-01/index.html	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	one off (may become a yearly event, to be confirmed later)	20-25 October 2019	theoretical and hands-on	EM	Ad hoc	EM	SEM, SBEM, Volume EM, 3D EM	SEM, SBEM, Volume EM, 3D EM
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Microinjection into adherent cells	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.de/training/events/2019/EPP19-03/index.html	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Autumn	29-30 October 2019	theoretical and hands-on	Phase contrast imaging; other: microinjection	Ad hoc	-	microinjection; adherent cells; phase contrast	microinjection, adherent cells, phase contrast
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	EMBO Course on in situ CLEM at room temperature and in cryo	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/lem25-01/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person		09-02-25	theoretical and hands on	CLEM	Ad hoc	CLEM		CLEM
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Imaging Mouse Development	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/imd24-01/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	Hybrid	Autumn	2 - 5 Sep 2024	theoretical and hands on	Advanced microscopy, Animal Imaging, Data Analysis	Periodic		in vivo/ex vivo imaging, sample preparation and clearing, 3D imaging restoration, image processing	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	C. elegans, from genome editing to imaging	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/cel24-01/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Summer	9-15 June 2024	theoretical and hands on	Optogenetics, Disease Modeling	Periodic		Optogenetics, Disease Modeling	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Imaging-based spatial-omics	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/iso25-01/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Summer	15 - 20 Jun 2025	theoretical and hands on	Spatial-omics, Data Analysis	Periodic		Spatial-omics, Data Analysis	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Advances in cryo-electron microscopy and 3D image processing	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/cry24-01/?utm_source=annu_alposter&utm_medium=poster&utm_id=CRY24-01	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Summer	18 - 26 Aug 2024	theoretical and hands on	EM	Periodic		Cryo-EM, Data Analysis	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Autumn School on Single Particle CryoEM: from Sample to 3D Reconstruction	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/imagining-centre/42599-2/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Autumn	7 - 11 October 2024	theoretical and hands on	EM	Periodic		Cryo-EM, Data Analysis	
Biological Imaging	EMBL-Heidelberg	Euro-Biolmaging EMBL-Node	Imaging down to single-molecule resolution: STED and MINFLUX nanoscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.embl.org/about/info/cou/rse-and-conference-office/events/eic24-01/?utm_source=annu_alposter&utm_medium=poster&utm_id=EIC24-01%20	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg	In-person	Autumn	21 - 26 Oct 2024	theoretical and hands on	STED	Ad hoc		STED, MINFLUX, nanoscopy	
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Bioimage Informatics 1 - Basic image processing and analysis	Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://digicampus.fi/course/view.php?id=14	University of Turku, Åbo Akademi University (online)	In-person	repeating		theoretical	Image processing and data analysis	Periodic	Image processing and data analysis	online; image analysis; image processing	image analysis, image processing
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Advanced image analysis course	Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://link.webpolsurveys.com/S/4D865B5700B6F09C	University of Turku, Åbo Akademi University (physical)	In-person	single time	20-22 Nov 2019	theoretical and hands-on	Image processing and data analysis	Ad hoc	Image processing and data analysis	image analysis; ImageJ; Fiji; ImageJ macro programming; ImageJ batch processing; segmentation; 3D segmentation; co-localization	image analysis, segmentation, colocalization, ImageJ macro programming
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Bioimage Informatics 2	Data Analysis	User training	https://studiehandboken.abo.fi/en/course/BY00BM39/8096?period=2020-2022	University of Turku	In-person		01 February - 31 March 2021			Ad hoc		Data analysis (T, H)	Image data, Image analysis, machine learning
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Automated Bioimage Analysis	Data Analysis	User training	https://opas.peppi.uu.fi/en/course/BIMA3221/19881?period=2020-2022	University of Turku	In-person		15 March - 25 May 2021			Ad hoc		Data analysis (T, H)	Machine learning, Image data, Image analysis

Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Quantification of histopathology using image analysis	Data Analysis	User training	https://opas.peppi.uu.fi/en/course/FIMA3222/233217/period=2020-2022	University of Turku	In-person		Spring 2021		Ad hoc	Data analysis (T, H)	Machine learning, Image data, Image analysis
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Histology and Histopathology	Data Analysis	User training	https://studiehandboken.abo.fi/en/course/2220540723?period=2020-2022	Abo Akademi University	In-person		07 March 07 May 2021		Ad hoc	Data analysis (T, H)	Image data, Image analysis
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Advanced Microscopy lectures	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Educational training	https://studiehandboken.abo.fi/en/course/2230980743?period=2020-2022	Abo Akademi University	In-person		11 January - 21 March 2021		Ad hoc	LSCM, TIRF, STED, SIM, STORM, FRET, FRAP, FLIM, Image processing and data analysis (T, H)	super-resolution microscopy, image analysis
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Imaging techniques lecture course, Light Microscopy & Electron Microscopy Basics	Technical	User training, Educational training	https://courses.helsinki.fi/en/lis-111	University of Helsinki	In-person		September 2021		Ad hoc	LSCM, EM	fundamentals of light microscopy and electron microscopy
Biological Imaging	FI	Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node	Practical course in Light Microscopy	Technical	User training	https://www.helsinki.fi/en/news/teaching-studying-at-the-university/lis-135-practical-course-in-electron-microscopy	University of Helsinki	In-person		November/December 2021		Ad hoc	EM	TEM, SEM
Both	FI	Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node	In Vivo Animal Imaging: Methods and Applications symposium & course	Technical	Educational training	https://eurobioimaging.fi/FBI/events/in-vivo-animal-imaging-methods-and-applications-virtual-course/	Helsinki In Vivo Animal Imaging Platform, University of Helsinki	In-person	yearly	Dec 13, 2021 - Jan 17, 2022	theoretical and hands on	Periodic	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Multiphoton microscopy systems, (Micro)-PET, (Micro)-SPECT, (Micro)-CT, In vivo Optical Imaging, (Micro)-PET/CT, (Micro)-SPECT/CT	intravital imaging; intravital microscopy; in vivo imaging; micro-CT, PET, SPECT; radio tracer; in vivo optical imaging
Medical Imaging	FI	Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node	Principles And Applications of Neuroimaging Data Analysis	Technical, Data Analysis	User training	https://emolion.uu.fi/neurocourse-2/	University of Turku	In-person	one time course	18-20 August 2021	theoretical and hands-on	Ad hoc	PET or (micro)PET, MR/MRS, high field MR/MRS, MRI-PET	human neuroimaging; preprocessing; image analysis; PET, MRI, fMRI; neuroinformatics
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Winter school on fluorescent markers	Technical	User training	https://fluorescencelehighouches.wordpress.com	École de physique des Houches	In-person		10.04.2022-15.04.2022	theoretical and hands on	Ad hoc	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM,	Fluorescent proteins and dyes, photophysics
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy Remote Training	Technical, Data Analysis	User training, Educational training	https://france.bioimaging.org/application/sf-n-remote-training/	Remote: Videos on FBI Youtube Channel + Live Q&A session on ZOOM	Virtual	Winter (every year)	15 Feb-5 March 2021 Videos available for registered participants from Feb. 15th to March 5th, 2021, Live Q&A on March 5th 2021	theoretical and hands-on	Periodic	Light-Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy, Single Plane Illumination Microscope, Lattice Light Sheet Microscope	Remote, Training, Light-Sheet Microscopy, LSFM, 3D, Imaging, Data Visualisation, soSPIM, LLSM, Ultramicroscope, diSPIM, clearing methods
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Image Analysis using Fiji	Data Analysis	User training	https://enseignement.curie.fr/cours/bases-de-lanalyse-dimages-sous-fiji-1	FR - Institut Curie	In-person	twice a year (French in spring, English in Autumn) - comment from Fede: I think we should only include the Autumn course...	October-December 2019	theoretical and hands-on	Periodic	LSCM/CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy	Image analysis/Fiji/image treatment/hands-on
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Image treatment and analysis with ImageJ-FIJI-ICY	Data Analysis	User training	https://cnrsformation.cars.fr/liste-stages-122-Microscopie-et-imagerie.html	FR - IBDM (Developmental Biology Institute of Marseille)	In-person	3 times a year	27-30/04/2020	theoretical and hands-on	Periodic	LSCM/CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, Electron Microscopy, In vivo Optical Imaging, Population Imaging	imagej ; fiji; icy; convolution; morphomathematics ; quality ; threshold; fft; object counter; 3D; tracking
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Fluorescence markers for advanced microscopy : From photophysics to biology	Technical	User training	https://fluorescencelehighouches.wordpress.com/	FR - MARS (Montpellier advanced microscopy research and development facility)	In-person	Spring	29/3-3/4/2020	Theoretical	Ad hoc	LSCM /CLSM; SDCM; Deconvolution widefield microscopy; Multiphoton microscopy systems; TIRF; STED; PALM; STORM; RESOLFT; GSD; GSDIM; FCS; FCCS; FLIM; FRET; FRAP; CLEM	Fluorescence; Photophysics; fluorophores; fluorescent proteins
Biological Imaging	FR	French Biolmaging Node	Super-resolution in photonic microscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	http://www.bic.u-bordeaux.fr/training_2020/	FR - Bordeaux Imaging Center	In-person	Spring	26-29/05/2020	theoretical and hands-on	Ad hoc	TIRF, STED, PALM, STORM, RESOLFT, GSD, GSDIM	super-resolution microscopy; PALM; STORM; STED; U-PAINT
Biological Imaging	IL	Israel Biolmaging	Data Science in Cell Imaging	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://sassafer.wixsite.com/dsci2021	Ben-Gurion University of the Negev	In-person	yearly	Feb 27 - June 24, 2022	theoretical	Periodic	Image analysis	data driven modeling, deep learning, data science
Biological Imaging	NL	Correlative Light Microscopy Dutch Flagship Node	Practical Course on Cryosectioning and Immuno-Electron Microscopy	Technical	User training	https://cellbiology-utrecht.nl/electron-microscopy-courses/cryosectioning-and-immuno-electron-microscopy.html	University Medical Centre Utrecht	In-person	Winter/Spring	20-23.01.2020	theoretical and hands-on	Ad hoc	DWM, EM, CLEM	Electron Microscopy; Sample Preparation; Ultrathin Cryosectioning; Immuno-gold Labelling; Correlative Light and Electron Microscopy

Biological Imaging	NL	Correlative Light Microscopy Dutch Flagship Node	Practical Course on Resin Electron Microscopy	Technical	User training	https://cellbiology-utrecht.nl/electron-microscopy-courses/resin-electron-microscopy.html	University Medical Centre Utrecht	In-person	Winter/Spring	15-17.01.2020	theoretical and hands-on	EM	Ad hoc	EM	Electron Microscopy; Sample Preparation; Resin Embedding; Ultrathin Sectioning	electron microscopy, sample preparation, resin embedding, ultrathin sectioning
Biological Imaging	NL	Correlative Light Microscopy Dutch Flagship Node	Cellular Imaging	Technical	Educational training	http://bcs.umcg.nl/en/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2020/02/2020-CI-courses.pdf	UMC Groningen	In-person	yearly	14-24 April 2020	theoretical and hands-on	Laser scanning confocal microscope (LSCM / CLSM), Spinning disc confocal microscopy (SDCM), Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, Total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy (TIRF), Stimulated emission depletion microscopy (STED), Photo activated localization microscopy (PALM), Stochastic optical reconstruction microscopy (STORM), Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS), Fluorescence cross-correlation spectroscopy (FCCS), Fluorescence-lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), Fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET), Fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP), High-throughput microscopy, Electron microscopy, Correlative light electron microscopy (CLEM), Selective plane illumination microscopy (SPIM), Digital scanned laser light-sheet fluorescence microscopy(DSLM), In vivo Optical Imaging	Periodic		cellular imaging	
Medical Imaging	NL	Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht	Artificial Intelligence 4 Imaging Radiomics, Deep Learning, Synthetic Data and Distributed Learning - a hands-on course	Technical, Data Analysis	Educational training	https://www.ai4imaging.org/	Maastricht University	In-person	one-time course	8-11 december 2021	theoretical and hands-on	(Micro)-PET, (Micro)-SPECT, (Micro)-MRI, (Micro)-CT, (Micro)-PET/CT, (Micro)-MRI/PET(SPECT), MRI-PET	Periodic		AI, medical imaging, clinical decision support, precision medicine	
Medical Imaging	NL	Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht	Course on Advanced Optical Microscopy	Technical	User training, Educational training	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/research/genetics-and-cell-biology/education https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/education/partner-program-master-master-biomedical-sciences/specialisations#Oncology	Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam	In-person	yearly	7-11 June 2021	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, Multiphoton microscopy systems, STED, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, High-throughput microscopy SPIM	Periodic		in vivo/ex vivo imaging, sample preparation and clearing, 3D imaging restoration, image processing	
Medical Imaging	NL	Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht	Imaging: from molecule to man	Technical, Data Analysis	Educational training	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/education/partner-program-master-master-biomedical-sciences/specialisations#Oncology	Maastricht University	In-person	yearly	6 jan - 28 feb 2020	theoretical and hands-on	High-field MRI, MRI-PET, MRS, PET-CT	Periodic		clinical Imaging; digital pathology	
Both	NL	Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht	Course on Advanced Optical Microscopy	Technical	User training, Educational training	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/phdpostdoc-course-advanced-optical-microscopy-2019	Maastricht University	In-person	yearly	June 2020	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM / CLSM, Multiphoton microscopy systems, STED, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, High-throughput microscopy SPIM	Periodic		in vivo/ex vivo imaging, sample preparation and clearing, 3D imaging restoration, image processing	
Medical Imaging	NL	Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht	Noninvasive imaging	Technical	User training, Educational training	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/sites/intranet.mumc.maastrichtuniversity.nl/files/canmmaasrichtin/public_new_events/flyer_2018_a4_carim_courses_maastricht_cd18.5141.pdf	Maastricht University Medical Center	In-person	yearly	June 2020	theoretical and hands-on	(micro)-PET, (micro)-SPECT, (micro)-MRI, (micro)-US, high field MRI, MRI-PET	Periodic		preclinical imaging	
Biological Imaging	NL	The Van Leeuwenhoek Center for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM) - Functional Imaging Flagship Node Amsterdam	Basics in Fluorescence Microscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	http://www.microscopycourse.nl/?page_id=78	LCAM-FNWI lab at Un Amsterdam	In-person	January (4 days)	28-31 January 2020	theoretical and hands-on	Wide- and confocal microscopy	Periodic	LSCM	Training on standard imaging methods (wide- and confocal microscopy)	standard imaging methods, widefield microscopy, confocal microscopy
Biological Imaging	NL	The Van Leeuwenhoek Center for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM) - Functional Imaging Flagship Node Amsterdam	Functional Imaging	Technical	User training, Educational training	http://www.microscopycourse.nl/?page_id=652	3 LCAM labs within Amsterdam	In-person	October (8 days)	7-16 October 2019	theoretical and hands-on	Functional Imaging, Super-resolution microscopy, CLEM	Periodic	FRET, FLIM, FCS, LSCM, SDCM, CLEM	- Measuring intra- and inter-molecular protein interactions using FRET, FLIM & FCS - Confocal microscopy methods including spinning disk (CLSM) - Superresolution microscopy - Confocal quality control - Correlative microscopy (bridging fluorescence microscopy and electron microscopy) - Usage of fluorophores such as FIAsh/ReAsh	intra- and inter-molecular protein interactions, super-resolution microscopy, quality control, use of fluorophores
Medical Imaging	NL	Population Imaging Flagship Node Rotterdam	Big Data Analytics: What, why and how?	Technical	Educational training	www.nihes.nl	Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam	In-person	yearly	August 2020	theoretical and hands-on	Population imaging, Challenges framework	Periodic		big data, bias, epidemiology, analytics, programming	

Medical Imaging	NL	Predclinical Imaging Centre (PRIME) - Molecular Imaging Dutch Node	In vivo NMR course	Technical	Educational training	https://www.isnmr-benelux.org/event/16th-in-vivo-nmr-course/	Radboud Medical Center	In-person	Autumn (once a year)	21-25/10/2019	theoretical and hands-on	(Micro)-MRI, High-field MRI	Periodic	High-field MRI, Micro-MRI	in vivo; MRI; MRS	in vivo, MRI, MRS
Biological Imaging	NL	Wageningen Imaging and Spectroscopy Hub (WISH) - ALM and Molecular Imaging Node Wageningen	Microspectroscopy: Functional Imaging of Biological Systems	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://microspectroscopy2021.febevents.org/	Microspectroscopy Research Facility Wageningen of Wageningen University & Research and Microscopic Imaging Centre of Radboud Institute for Molecular Life Sciences	In-person	Autumn (Every 2nd year)	14 -23 Sept 2021	theoretical and hands-on	Microscopic and spectroscopic techniques for studying biological processes in living cells	Periodic	LSCM, MMS, TIRF, FRET, FLIM, FCS, FRAP, PALM, STORM, STED	Confocal microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy, Photo-activatable imaging, Single particle tracking, Total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy, Super-Resolution and Correlative Microscopy, Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), FRET imaging techniques, Fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM), Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS), Multi dimensional Fluorescence, Fluorescence recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP)	microscopic and spectroscopic techniques, super-resolution, biological processes, living cells
Biological Imaging	NL	Wageningen Imaging and Spectroscopy Hub (WISH) - ALM and Molecular Imaging Node Wageningen	Advanced Course Microscopy and Spectroscopy in Food and Plant Sciences Functional imaging of biological systems	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.viagraduateschool.nl/en/showpages/show/msfp25.htm	Microspectroscopy Research Facility Wageningen of Wageningen University & Research and Microscopic Imaging Centre of Radboud Institute for Molecular Life Sciences	In-person		1/27/25	theoretical and hands-on	Microscopic and spectroscopic techniques for studying biological processes in living cells	Ad hoc	LSCM, MMS, TIRF, FRET, FLIM, FCS, FRAP, PALM, STORM, STED	Confocal microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy, Photo-activatable imaging, Single particle tracking, Total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy, Super-Resolution and Correlative Microscopy, Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), FRET imaging techniques, Fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM), Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS), Multi dimensional Fluorescence, Fluorescence recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP)	microscopic and spectroscopic techniques, super-resolution, biological processes, living cells
Biological Imaging	NO	NorMIC Oslo - Advanced Light Microscopy Node Oslo	5th NorMIC Workshop on Microscopy image Processing	Data Analysis	User training	https://nettskema.uio.no/a/121875	University of Oslo	In-person	Spring and Autumn (twice a year)	21-25 October 2019	theoretical and hands-on	LSCM/CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, TIRF, PALM, STORM, FRAP, CLEM, SPIM,	Periodic	LSCM, SDCM, DWM, TIRF, PALM, STORM, FRAP, CLEM, SPIM, image processing and data analysis	deconvolution, edge detection, filtering, image restoration, imaging, macros, photometry, sampling, scripts, segmentation, tracking	image processing and restoration, segmentation, macros, tracking
Biological Imaging	PT	Portuguese Platform of BiImaging (PPBI)	BioImage Analysis for High Content Screening Course on Optical Microscopy	Data Analysis	Educational training	https://www.i3s.up.pt/training-detail.php?v=151	i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto	In-person	yearly	25-28 May 2021	practical and hands-on		Periodic		high content screening	ImageJ/Fiji, ilastik, CellProfiler, CellProfiler Analyst, Cytoscape and IDEAS®
Biological Imaging	PT	Portuguese Platform of BiImaging (PPBI)	High Throughput Screening and Image Analysis for BioSciences	Technical	User training	https://www.i3s.up.pt/training-detail.php?v=204	i3S - University of Porto	In-person	yearly	28.03.2022-01.04.2022	theoretical and hands on	LSCM / CLSM, SDCM, Deconvolution widefield microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy systems, PALM, STORM, FLIM, FRET, FRAP, OCPI, DSLM	Periodic		Light microscopy, sample preparation, nanoscopy, mesoscopy, image analysis	
Biological Imaging	PT	Portuguese Platform of BiImaging (PPBI)	Introduction to digital bioimage analysis	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.i3s.up.pt/training-detail.php?v=201	i3S - University of Porto	In-person	yearly	23.05.2022-27.05.2022	theoretical and hands on	High throughput microscopy	Periodic		High throughput microscopy, image analysis	
Biological Imaging	PT	Portuguese Platform of BiImaging (PPBI)	Introduction to digital bioimage analysis	Data Analysis	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.i3s.up.pt/training-detail.php?v=202	i3S - University of Porto	In-person	yearly	26.09.2022-30.09.2022	hands on	BioImage Analysis	Periodic		Image analysis	
Biological Imaging	SE	Swedish National Microscopy Infrastructure (NMI)	Online Applied Microscopy Course	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.research-and-environments/core-facilities-for-research/live-cell-imaging-core-facility/ci/ci-microscopy-course	Karoliska Institute	In-person	yearly	January 27–February 14, 2025	virtual	LSCM / CLSM	Periodic	LSCM	Light microscopy, sample preparation, fluorescence, confocal	
Biological Imaging	UK	The UK Node	Hands-On Confocal Microscopy	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.york.ac.uk/biology/technology/facility/fcourses/confocal-course/	York University	In-person	yearly	April 1–4, 2025	hands on	LSCM / CLSM	Periodic	LSCM, MMS, TIRF, FRET, FLIM, FCS, FRAP, PALM, STORM, STED	Confocal microscopy, Multiphoton microscopy, Photo-activatable imaging, Single particle tracking, Total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy, Super-Resolution and Correlative Microscopy, Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), FRET imaging techniques, Fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM), Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS), Multi dimensional Fluorescence, Fluorescence recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP)	
Biological Imaging	UK	The UK Node	Light Microscopy Summer School 2025	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.mms.org.uk/mms-event-calendar/2025-events/light-microscopy-summer-school-2025.html	York University	In-person	yearly	June 9–10, 2025		LSCM / CLSM	Periodic		Light microscopy, sample preparation, fluorescence, confocal	
Biological Imaging	UK	The UK Node	Getting the most from your Confocal Course 2025	Technical	User training, Facility Staff training	https://www.mms.org.uk/mms-event-calendar/2025-events/getting-the-most-from-your-confocal-course-2025.html	York University	In-person	yearly	June 11–12, 2025		LSCM / CLSM	Periodic		Confocal microscopy, Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS), Multi dimensional Fluorescence, Fluorescence recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP)	

Annex B - Externally Organised Training Courses

Annex B - Externally Organised Training Courses												
Course Title	Geography	Area	Bio/Med	Keywords	Format	Organiser	Specific organiser	Year Period	Specific Dates	Training Availability	Link	
MLMC (Montreal Light Microscopy Course) In-Focus STimulated Emission Depletion (STED) Microscopy	CA	Technical	Biological Imaging	Super-resolution Microscopy	In-person	Biolumaging North America	McGill University	Spring	July 21-25	Periodic	https://www.canadabioimaging.org/mlmc-infocus-sted	
2025 QuPath Training Course: From Samples to Knowledge	Virtual	Technical, Data	Both	Spatial-omics	Virtual	Biolumaging North America	La Jolla Institute		February 24–26, 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/2025-qupath-training-course-from-samples-to-knowledge-registration-1117012677989?aff=oddtcreator	
Cryo-Electron Microscopy	US	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Cryo-EM, Data Analysis	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Cold Spring Harbor Lab	Winter	March 5 - 19, 2025	Periodic	https://meetings.cshl.edu/courses.aspx?course=C-CRYOEM	
Imaging Mouse Development	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Advanced microscopy, Animal Imaging, Data Analysis	Hybrid	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBO	Autumn	2 - 5 Sep 2024	Periodic	https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/imd24-01/	
C. elegans, from genome editing to imaging	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical	Biological Imaging	Optogenetics, Disease Modeling	In-person	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBO	Summer	9–15 June 2024	Periodic	https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/cel24-01/	
Imaging-based spatial-omics	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Spatial-omics, Data Analysis	In-person	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBO	Summer	15 - 20 Jun 2025	Periodic	https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/iso25-01/	
Advances in cryo-electron microscopy and 3D image processing	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Cryo-EM, Data Analysis	In-person	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBO	Summer	18 - 26 Aug 2024	Periodic	https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/cry24-01/?utm_source=annualposter&utm_medium=poster&utm_id=CRY24-01	
Autumn School on Single Particle CryoEM: from Sample to 3D Reconstruction	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Cryo-EM, Data Analysis	In-person	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBO	Autumn	7 – 11 October 2024	Ad hoc	https://www.embl.org/about/info/imaging-centre/42599-2/	
Imaging down to single-molecule resolution: STED & MINFLUX nanoscopy	EMBL Heidelberg	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Super-resolution Microscopy, Data Analysis	In-person	EMBL/EMBO, Euro-Biolumaging Node	EMBL	Autumn	21 - 26 Oct 2024	Ad hoc	https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/sic24-01/?utm_source=annualposter&utm_medium=poster&utm_id=IC24-01%20	
Imaging Structure & Function in the Nervous System	US	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Neuroimaging, Data Analysis	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Cold Spring Harbor Lab	Summer	July 22 - August 12, 2025	Periodic	https://meetings.cshl.edu/courses.aspx?course=C-IMAG	
Optical Microscopy & Imaging in the Biomedical Sciences (OMIBS)	US	Technical	Both	Advanced microscopy, Super-resolution Microscopy, Data Analysis	In-person	Biolumaging North America	MBL Woods Hole	Summer	Aug 12-22	Periodic	https://www.mbl.edu/education/advanced-research-training-courses/course-offerings/optical-microscopy-imaging-biomedical-sciences	
Quantitative Imaging: From Acquisition to Analysis	US	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis, Advanced microscopy	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Cold Spring Harbor Lab	Spring	Mar 24 – Apr 8	Periodic	https://meetings.cshl.edu/courses.aspx?course=C-QICM	
Quantitative Fluorescence Microscopy	US	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Fluorescence Microscopy, Data Analysis	In-person	Biolumaging North America	MDI Biological Laboratory	Spring	May 16-23, 2025	Periodic	https://mdibl.org/course/gfm-2025/	
Leadership and Management in Core Facilities	US	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Northwestern, Kellogg	Summer	June 9-12	Periodic	https://www.kellogg.northwestern.edu/executive-education/nonprofit-management/np-core.aspx	
Light Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy	US	Technical	Biological Imaging	Fluorescence Microscopy	In-person	Biolumaging North America	MDI Biological Laboratory	Summer	June 1-7, 2025	Periodic	https://mdibl.org/course/lsvm-2025/	
Annual Workshop on FLIM, FRET and Label-free Metabolic Imaging	US	Technical	Biological Imaging	Fluorescence Microscopy, Metabolic Imaging	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Keck Center for Cellular Imaging	Summer	June 9-13, 2025	Periodic	https://kcci.virginia.edu/workshop-2025	
Tissue Clearing Workshop	US	Technical	Both	Sample preparation, Advanced microscopy	In-person	Biolumaging North America	Harvard University	Winter	February 10-12, 2025	Periodic	https://micron.hms.harvard.edu/tissue-clearing-workshop-2025	
CTLS Professional Development Course for Core Facility Staff	Virtual	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management	Virtual	Core Technologies for Life Sciences (CTLS)	CTLS	2025	March 25 to April 10, 2025	Periodic	https://ctls.org.eu	
Webinar: Improving facility user trainings with pedagogy: an interactive workshop	Virtual	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management	Virtual	Core Technologies for Life Sciences (CTLS)	CTLS	2025	12 March 2025	Ad hoc	https://ctls.org.eu/events/improving-facility-using-trainings/	
Microscopy data analysis: machine learning and the Biolumage Archive	EMBL - EBI, Hinxton	Data	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis	Virtual	EMBL/EMBO	EMBL-EBI	Spring	Mar 31 – Apr 4	Periodic	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/microscopy-data-analysis-2025/	
LINDoscope: Neuroimaging and data analysis	DE	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Neuroimaging, Data Analysis	In-person	EMBL/EMBO	EMBO	Autumn	04 – 15 September 2023	Ad hoc	https://meetings.embo.org/event/23-lindoscope	
Imaging Marine Organisms Across Scales	IT	Technical	Biological Imaging	Multimodal imaging, Marine Biology	In-person	EMBL/EMBO	EMBO	Spring	9–12 April 2024	Ad hoc	https://meetings.embo.org/event/24-marine-imaging	
3D developmental imaging	PT	Technical	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis, Advanced microscopy, Optical tomography	In-person	EMBL/EMBO	EMBO	Summer	1–9 July 2022	Periodic	https://meetings.embo.org/event/18-developmental-imaging	
Two-photon imaging of brain circuit function	CH	Technical	Biological Imaging	Two-photon imaging, Neuroimaging	In-person	EMBL/EMBO	EMBO	Summer	03 – 09 September 2017	Periodic	https://meetings.embo.org/event/17-two-photon	
RITrainPlus: Continuous Professional Development (CPD) courses	IT	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management, Research Infrastructure Management	Hybrid	EU-Projects	RITrainPlus	Winter	November	Periodic	https://ritrainplus.eu/course-catalogue/	
WORKSHOP: Remote access for electron microscopy	Virtual	Technical, Operations	Biological Imaging	Cryo-EM, Data Analysis, Service provision	Virtual	EU-Projects	Euro-Biolumaging		June 20,2024	Ad hoc	https://www.czech-bioimaging.cz/news/workshop-remote-access-for-electron-microscopy	
ANERIS Workshops on Underwater Imaging, Bio-optic, and Participatory Technologies	Virtual	Technical	Biological Imaging	Underwater imaging	Virtual	EU-Projects	Euro-Biolumaging		November 7,2024	Ad hoc	https://aneris.eu/news/aneris-workshops-underwater-imaging-bio-optic-and-participatory-technologies	

Annex B - Externally Organised Training Courses

Guide to FAIR BioImage Data	Virtual	Data, Operations	Both	FAIR training	Virtual	Euro-BioImaging	Euro-BioImaging			Periodic	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/our-events/image-data-events/guide-to-fair-bioimage-data/
Webinar on Data Management of Preclinical Image Datasets	Virtual	Data, Operations	Biomedical Imaging	FAIR training	Virtual	Euro-BioImaging	Euro-BioImaging			Ad hoc	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/events/data-management-of-preclinical-image-datasets/
Industry resources for Euro-BioImaging Nodes	Multiple locations	Technical	Both	Industry training	Virtual	Euro-BioImaging, Industry	EBIB			Ad hoc	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/training/industry-resources/
Multiscale Imaging Workshop - From single cells to entire organisms	DE	Technical	Both	Advanced microscopy, Magnetic Resonance in Imaging, PET/CT	In-person	European Society For Molecular Imaging (ESMI)	Werner Siemens Imaging Center	2025	February 10 – 14, 2025	Ad hoc	http://www.isct.uni-tuebingen.de/wsic/multiscale-immunoimaging-workshop
GerBI Core Facility Leadership and Management Course	DE	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management	In-person	German BioImaging	German BioImaging	Summer	August 11-16, 2025	Periodic	https://gerbi-qmb.de/event/gerbi-qmb-core-facility-leadership-and-management-course-2025/
Molecules to Human (M2H) boot camp	DK	Technical, Data	Both	Advanced microscopy, Animal Imaging, Data Analysis	In-person	Global BioImaging	Danish Bioimaging			Ad hoc	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
OMERO: Management, sharing, publication and analysis of image data	Virtual	Data	Both	Data Analysis	Virtual	Global BioImaging	ABIS			Periodic	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
Webinar of Image Data Resource (IDR)	Virtual	Data	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis	Virtual	Global BioImaging	ABIS			Ad hoc	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
AMP-EVIDENT Basic Microscopy Course 2025	SG	Technical	Biological Imaging	Fluorescence Microscopy	In-person	Global BioImaging	Singascope		February 25–28, 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.singascope.sg/event/amp-evident-basic-microscopy-course-2025/
Global BioImaging Train-the-Trainer Course	Multiple locations	Professional development	Both	Train-the-trainer	In-person	Global BioImaging	GBI			Periodic	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
Global BioImaging Image Data Course	Multiple locations	Data	Both	Data Analysis	In-person	Global BioImaging	GBI			Periodic	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
Global BioImaging Facility Management Course	Multiple locations	Professional development	Both	Core Facility Management	In-person	Global BioImaging	GBI			Periodic	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
Bioimage hackathon: Implementaion of deep learning models	Multiple locations	Data	Both	Data Analysis	In-person	Global BioImaging	GBI			Periodic	https://globalbioimaging.org/international-training-courses
Image Analysis course with Fiji/ImageJ	Virtual	Data	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis	Virtual	Industry	Pixel Biology Ltd		February 10–14, 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/image-analysis-course-with-fiji-imagej-tickets-1110540058209
Leveraging The Imaging Capabilities of the ZEISS Gemini FESEM On Life Science Samples Using ATLAS 5	Virtual	Technical, Operations	Biological Imaging	Electron microscopy	Virtual	Industry	ZEISS		February 13, 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.zeiss.com/microscopy/us//events/workshops/leveraging-the-imaging-capabilities-of-the-zeiss-gemini-fesem.html
ZEN Blue Software: Mastering Modules	Virtual	Data	Biological Imaging	Data Analysis	Virtual	Industry	ZEISS		26 February 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.zeiss.com/microscopy/us//events/workshops/zen-blue-workshop-zmcc.html
ISMRM Workshop on Perfusion MRI: Found in Translation	ES	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM)	ISMRM	2025	15-17 March 2025	Ad hoc	https://scmr.org/isrmr-co-provided-workshop/
SCMR-ISMRM Co-Provided Workshop on Cutting-Edge Imaging of Cardiac Microstructure, Motion & Strain	US	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM)	ISMRM	2025	29-30 January 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.isrmr.org/workshops/2025/Perfusion/
ISMRM Workshop on Body MRI: Unsolved Problems & Unmet Needs	US	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM)	ISMRM	2025	28-30 March 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.isrmr.org/workshops/2025/Body/
ISMRM Joint Workshop of the Ultra-High Field MR & Brain Function Study Groups	US	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM)	ISMRM	2025	31 March-02 April 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.isrmr.org/workshops/2025/UHF-Brain/
ISMRM Workshop on Metabolomics & Metabolomic Imaging in Medicine: Challenges & Opportunities	IT	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	International society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine (ISMRM)	ISMRM	2025	16-18 October 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.isrmr.org/workshops/2025/MMI/
GloBIAS Webinar Series	Virtual	Data	Both	Data Analysis	Virtual	Online community	GloBIAS			Periodic	https://www.globias.org/activities/bia-seminar-series
Electron Microscopy Spring School 2025	UK	Technical, Data	Biological Imaging	Electron microscopy	In-person	Royal Microscopical Society (RMS)	University of Leeds		March 31–April 4, 2025	Periodic	https://www.rms.org.uk/rms-event-calendar/2025-events/electron-microscopy-spring-school-2025.html
Early Professionals Forum Webinar Series	Virtual	Professional development	Biomedical Imaging	Molecular Imaging	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2022		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/sanjiv-sam-gambhir-early-professionals-forum-webinar-series/
Theranostics Webinar Series	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Theragnostics, Molecular Imaging	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2021		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/theranostics-webinar-series/
COVID-19 Webinar Series	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	COVID-19, Molecular Imaging, Multimodal imaging	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2020		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/covid-19-webinar-series/
Imaging of Infection Webinar Series	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	infectious disease, Molecular Imaging	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2020		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/imaging-of-infection-webinar-series/
Immune Cell Imaging Webinar Series	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Immunology, Molecular Imaging	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2020		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/immune-cell-imaging-webinar-series/
WMIS Webinar Series	Virtual	Technical, Data	Biomedical Imaging	Molecular Imaging, Train-the-trainer, Data Analysis	Virtual	World Molecular Imaging Society	WMIS	2019-2025		Ad hoc	https://wmis.org/education/wmis-webinar-series/

Annex B - Externally Organised Training Courses

RF coils: Design, build and characterise your own	UK	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	In-person	European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology (ESMRMB)	School of Biomedical Engineering and Imaging Sciences, King's College London	2025	September 16-19, 2025	Ad hoc	https://www.esmrm-b.org/education/#m-homr
MRI Together: Global workshop on open, reproducible, and inclusive MR research	Virtual	Operations, Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging, Open Science	Virtual	European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology (ESMRMB)	ESMRMB	2024	December 3 to 6,	Ad hoc	https://mritogether.esmrm-b.org/24m/
Artificial Intelligence in Nuclear Medicine - Current Status and Future Perspective	AT	Technical, Data	Biomedical Imaging	Artificial Intelligence, Nuclear Medicine	In-person	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025	February 13 & 14	Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/artificial-intelligence-in-nuclear-medicine-current-status-and-future-perspective/
Advantages of Long-Axial Field-of-View PET in Inflammation and Infection Imaging	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	PET/CT	Virtual	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025		Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/advantages-of-long-axial-field-of-view-pet-in-inflammation-and-infection-imaging/
Cardiac Amyloidosis Imaging: History, Status Quo and Outlook	AT	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging, PET/CT	In-person	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025	March 20 & 21	Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/cardiac-amyloidosis-imaging-history-status-quo-and-outlook/
Highlights of Focus Meeting 6: Shaping the Future of Breast Cancer Care with Molecular Imaging	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Magnetic Resonance in Imaging	Virtual	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025		Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/highlights-of-focus-meeting-6-shaping-the-future-of-breast-cancer-care-with-molecular-imaging-prerecorded/
Cardiac Amyloidosis Imaging: Do We Need Quantification?	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	PET/CT	Virtual	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025	June 13	Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/cardiac-amyloidosis-imaging-do-we-need-quantification/
Focus on FDG PET/CT in Inflammatory and Infectious Diseases	AT	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	PET/CT	Virtual	European School of Multimodality Imaging & Therapy (ESMIT)	ESMIT	2025		Ad hoc	https://esmit.eanm.org/event/focus-on-fdg-pet-ct-in-inflammatory-and-infectious-diseases/
Micro-CT User Training	Multiple locations	Technical, Data	Biomedical Imaging	MicroCT	In-person	Industry	Brucker			Periodic	https://www.bruker.com/en/services/training/microtomography/micro-ct-user-training.html
Atomic Force Microscopy Training	Multiple locations	Technical	Biological Imaging	Advanced microscopy	In-person	Industry	Brucker			Periodic	https://www.bruker.com/en/services/training/atomic-force-microscopy.html
Shear Wave Elastography and High Frequency Ultrasound: Meet the Experts	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Ultrasound	Virtual	Industry	Visualsonics			Ad hoc	https://www.visualsonics.com/resource/webinars
PET Cardiac Training	Multiple locations	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	PET/CT	In-person	Industry	Phillips			Ad hoc	https://www.learningconnection.phillips.com/en/course/pet-cardiac-training?tid=2833
PET/CT 4D Respiratory Gating Training	Multiple locations	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	PET/CT	In-person	Industry	Phillips			Ad hoc	https://www.learningconnection.phillips.com/en/catalog/product-group/advanced-molecular-imaging/pet-ct
Hybrid Imaging	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Oncology	Virtual	European School of Radiology	ESOR			Ad hoc	https://www.esor.org/courses/foundation-courses/hybrid-imaging-2025/
Medical Imaging Informatics	Virtual	Technical	Biomedical Imaging	Data Analysis	Virtual	European School of Radiology	ESOR			Ad hoc	https://www.esor.org/courses/foundation-courses/medical-imaging-informatics-2025/

Euro-Biolmaging Node	To develop dedicated Training Courses for Node Staff, select what imaging technology training is more of a priority at your Node. Please be specific by adding details of the respective technology under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - select what other technical training you would be interested in (indicate all applicable). Please be specific by adding details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What aspects could help you to optimize daily operations at your facility? (indicate all applicable). Please provide details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What would you like to see as part of Euro-Biolmaging's curriculum for staff professional development? (indicate all applicable)	Training with Industry - What areas of innovation, intellectual property rights (IPR), and collaboration with industry would you like to see reflected in a training course or workshop?
NMI, Sweden	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	Management innovation; co-creation, Engagement with industry
BioimagingUK - ESRIC	Advanced light microscopy		Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	Don't know
BIN-Portugal	Animal imaging, Human imaging, MRI-PET-Neurophysiology	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution	AI
Austria	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, protocol development	Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
Belgian Node	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
Flanders Biolmaging	analysis		having more people		
Population Imaging Flagship Node Rotterdam	Human imaging	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), Medical image data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving	

Euro-Biolmaging Node	To develop dedicated Training Courses for Node Staff, select what imaging technology training is more of a priority at your Node. Please be specific by adding details of the respective technology under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - select what other technical training you would be interested in (indicate all applicable). Please be specific by adding details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What aspects could help you to optimize daily operations at your facility? (indicate all applicable). Please provide details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What would you like to see as part of Euro-Biolmaging's curriculum for staff professional development? (indicate all applicable)	Training with Industry - What areas of innovation, intellectual property rights (IPR), and collaboration with industry would you like to see reflected in a training course or workshop?
Swedish Node (Stockholm/KTH)	Advanced light microscopy	sample preparation, protocol development	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities	Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	Superresolution microscopy
FBI	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, How to extend the life of its instrumentation	innovation and extending life of instruments
Yes, Israel	Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
van Leeuwenhoek Centre for Advanced Microscopy	Advanced light microscopy, Functional imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)		
UK Bioimaging node	Animal imaging	sample preparation, protocol development	Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	
Austria	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), for microscopy	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Budgeting and Accounting	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	technical developments in electron microscopy; courses on first-level-support for equipment
BMIN, BLivin (Barcelona, Spain)	Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging, correlative imaging of all sorts (LM to other LM, LM to EM), Open Tools for HTS analysis		Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)		All aspects of transparency with IA innovations offered by Industry
Cellular Imaging Hungary	Advanced light microscopy	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management	
PPBI - Portugal	Advanced light microscopy, Data imaging processing	protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), for microscopy	Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	Building Industry Partnerships, Collaboration Strategies, Innovation Ecosystems, Tools and Resources

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UK - York	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)		Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management	
Center for Advanced Preclinical Imaging	Animal imaging, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	Data processing and analysis for medical image data			
Center for Advanced Preclinical Imaging (CAPI)	Animal imaging	protocol development	Deeper knowledge of the used imaging methods	I do not know.	I do not know.
France Biolmaging	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	ethics management, sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), Microscopy	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
UK	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	ethics management, sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), microscopy only, thanks	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	How to work with industry to co-develop IP
French Biolmaging	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging		Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
NMI Sweden	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, CLEM, SMLM	sample preparation, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), microscopy data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
CAPI	Animal imaging	animal handling, ethics management, protocol development, cohort recruitment	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	

Euro-Biolmaging Node	To develop dedicated Training Courses for Node Staff, select what imaging technology training is more of a priority at your Node. Please be specific by adding details of the respective technology under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - select what other technical training you would be interested in (indicate all applicable). Please be specific by adding details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What aspects could help you to optimize daily operations at your facility? (indicate all applicable). Please provide details under "other" at the end of the option list.	Training Courses for Node Staff - What would you like to see as part of Euro-Biolmaging's curriculum for staff professional development? (indicate all applicable)	Training with Industry - What areas of innovation, intellectual property rights (IPR), and collaboration with industry would you like to see reflected in a training course or workshop?
Israel		protocol development		Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	characterization nano materials, spintronic computers , antioxidants
Israel	Human imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	Image analysis
NorMIC Oslo - Advanced Light Microscopy Node Oslo	tomography (TEM and STEM), CLEM, immuno-EM	sample preparation, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), Microscopy	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Administration and personnel management, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
poland, warsaw	Advanced light microscopy	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), microscopy data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
Advanced Light Microscopy Node Poland	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), data processing for microscopy	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	data management
Institute of Molecular Biology - BAS, Sofia	Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	animal handling, sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
UK	Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Correlative imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), microscopy	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	

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NORMOLIM	Animal imaging, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	ethics management, protocol development, cohort recruitment	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops	Pharmaceutical industry
PPBI - Portuguese Platform of Bioimaging	Advanced light microscopy, Mostly widefield and confocal imaging (tiles, z-stacks, stereology, time series)	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data), These are the topics less developed at my facility	Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
AMMI	Animal imaging	animal handling, ethics management	Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users	
Phase Contrast Imaging	Animal imaging, Human imaging, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), Artificial Intelligence and machine learning approaches for medical images	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution	
MMMM	Animal imaging, Human imaging	animal handling, protocol development	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Administration and personnel management	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management	
Flanders Biolmaging Node (Belgium)	Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging, all advanced microscopy techniques where we try to image from organelle, over organ to organism	sample preparation, protocol development	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	research and development, application development, application specialist and technical service
Brno CZ node	Human imaging	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), medical image data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)		
Belgium	Animal imaging	animal handling, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), MRI	Budgeting and Accounting		NA
CF MAFIL, CEITEC Masaryk university, Brno, Czech Republic	Human imaging	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), medical image data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)		

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Flanders Biolmaging	Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), microscopy data analysis	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
MMMI	Animal imaging, Human imaging	Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), medical image data	Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)		
PPBI EuBI	Animal imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), Microscopy	Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
Italian Multi-sited Multi-Modal Molecular Imaging (MMMI) Node	Animal imaging	animal handling	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users		molecular imaging
MMMI Italian Node		protocol development	Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users	
Molecular Imaging Italian Node	Animal imaging, Human imaging, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging, MRI	animal handling, sample preparation, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), medical image data	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Administration and personnel management	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving	
PRIME	Animal imaging	animal handling, ethics management	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	
Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Italian Node	Animal imaging	animal handling, ethics management, sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data)	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution	
Italian	Animal imaging	animal handling	Administration and personnel management	Conflict resolution and problem solving	

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Medical and Precinical Imaging Hungary	Animal imaging	animal handling, sample preparation, protocol development	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Pro-active communication - to improve communication in my facility, lab, with users, How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution, Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	Patents in radiopharmacy
Flanders Biolmaging	Advanced light microscopy	sample preparation	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Budgeting and Accounting	How to talk to your funders - pitching your ideas to a broader audience, identify KOL at your institution	
Danish Biolmaging	Animal imaging, Human imaging, Advanced light microscopy, Electron microscopy, Ex-vivo, material and plant imaging	ethics management, sample preparation, protocol development, Data processing and analysis (please specify if for microscopy or medical image data), both	Quality Control in Imaging Facilities, Improving outreach and communication with users, Administration and personnel management, Budgeting and Accounting, Data management (storage, FAIR data, curation, handling sensitive data)	Time management - to support daily tasks and stress management, Conflict resolution and problem solving, Train-the-trainer 1 - the toolkit to design and run courses and workshops, Train-the-trainer 2 - the skillset in how to train others, my staff and/or users	co-development of new instruments/protocols